

A Descriptive Community-Based Cross-Sectional Study to Understand Knowledge and Attitude towards Cervical Cancer among Reproductive Age Group Women

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Abstract:

Background: The cervix, which connects the uterus and vagina, can develop cancer. This condition is known as cervical cancer. It is primarily caused by the sexually transmissible pathogen known as the Human Papilloma Virus (HPV). Consequently, cervical cancer can be avoided with efficient HPV infection prevention measures. The condition usually affects women who live in less affluent neighbourhoods. Research shows that 85% of all cervical cancer fatalities and about 83% of new cases worldwide occur in underdeveloped nations. Additionally, the study indicates that many countries' quick socio-economic transformation may lessen malignancies brought on by infections. But this could be changed. By a growing number of new instances that are more closely linked to nutritional, hormonal, and reproductive variables. Cervical cancer is quite uncommon in the developed nations worldwide.

Aim: The study aims to analyse a descriptive community-based cross-sectional study to understand knowledge and attitude towards cervical cancer among reproductive age group women.

Methods: This was a cross sectional descriptive study conducted at Dr DY Patil Medical College, Pimpri, Pune from April 2020 to March 2023. The study has included participants of all reproductive age women. The selection of population was done using the proportion formula considering the assumption 5% error margin ($d = 0.05$). To gather information, an interviewer-administered, pretested, structured, and modified questionnaire was used. The study's descriptive statistics, such as frequency, mean, and percent, were calculated with the SPSS software version 29.

Results: Around 65% of the participants have heard about the cervical cancer and only 40% have knowledge about the risk factors involve in this disease. In addition to this, 24.2% knew that the major factor of risk in this disease is smoking, followed by multiple sexual partner (22.0%) and poor dietary habits (20.2%). Moreover, the analysis has suggested that 82.0% participants didn't know that HPV is an agent of cervical cancer.

Conclusion: Participants' general understanding of cervical cancer and how to prevent it was insufficient. More than 80% of the participants were not aware that HPV is a factor that causes cervical cancer. This is really concerning because preventing HPV infection is the most effective approach to avoid cervical cancer. Apart from this, the finding of study has involved the main information source on cervical cancer was the mass media.

Keywords: Cervical Cancer, Knowledge, Attitude, Reproductive age group women

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Background

The cervix, which connects the uterus and vagina, can develop cancer. This condition is known as cervical cancer. It is primarily caused by the sexually transmissible pathogen known as the Human Papilloma Virus (HPV) [1]. Consequently, cervical cancer can be avoided with efficient HPV infection prevention measures. The condition usually affects women who live in less affluent neighbourhoods. Research shows that 85% of all cervical cancer

fatalities and about 83% of new cases worldwide occur in underdeveloped nations [2]. Cervical cancer is mostly caused by persistent infection with approximately 15 high-risk HPV strains; of these, HPV-16 and HPV-18 infections account for roughly 70% of cases [3]. Many romantic relationships, younger age at first sexual encounter, early marriage, unhealthy eating habits, weakened immune system, and

tobacco use also act as risk factors for the development of cancer and a chronic HPV infection [4].

Additionally, the study indicates that many countries' quick socio-economic transformation may lessen malignancies brought on by infections. But this could be changed [5]. By a growing number of new instances that are more closely linked to nutritional, hormonal and reproductive variables [6]. Cervical cancer is quite uncommon in the developed nations worldwide. The situation in developing nations, however, is quite the opposite [7]. In the former, the incidence is declining, while in the latter, it is increasing within South America, the Caribbean and Sub-Saharan Africa [8]. Cervical cancer is the primary cause of cancer-related deaths and early deaths among women in Southern Asia.

According to World Health Organization (WHO), the average outpatient cost per patient for cervical cancer is projected to be come to \$407.2. It was also projected that the average inpatient cost for hospitalised patients was \$404.4 [9]. The total cost of the inpatient stay was \$329, with an expected daily increase of \$4.2 for each extra day of hospitalisation [10]. As per the analysis, that is quite high and inconceivable for many patients to receive care given the socioeconomic standing of the populace [11].

According to the outcome of study on the health-seeking behaviours of individuals with cervical cancer also showed that women's knowledge of cervical cancer and the majority of them favour conventional treatments as a choice for early-stage treatment of the illness [12]. This study indicates that the obstacles to obtaining any kind of lack of awareness and access to appropriate health care were noted as treatments.

Aim

The study aims to analyse a descriptive community based cross-sectional study to understand

knowledge and attitude towards cervical cancer among reproductive age group women.

Method and material

This was a cross sectional descriptive study conducted at Dr DY Patil Medical College, Pimpri, Pune from April 2020 to March 2023. The study has included reproductive age women. The selection of population was done using the proportion formula considering the assumption 5% error margin ($d = 0.05$). After deducting the design effect from the 10% non-response rate, the total sample size was 800. In addition to this, random sampling technique was used for selection of the sample.

Variables and Data Collection

The variables that were considered for study involve the knowledge level of the individual. Moreover, the independent variable involves the socio-demographic measures like age, religion, income, occupation, and educational status. To gather information, an interviewer-administered, pretested, structured, and modified questionnaire was used. For the knowledge and attitude questions, each right answer was worth one point. The scores were then converted into a percentage for the purpose of interpreting the findings.

Data Analysis

The statistical programme Epi-data 3.1 was used to code and enter the data into a computer. After that, the data were exported to SPSS Version 29 for additional analysis. To reduce entry errors and check for anomalies, the data was cleaned and processed and unfilled values. Next, the study's descriptive statistics, such as frequency, mean, and percent, were calculated variables with the SPSS software version 29.

Results

Table 1: Demographic Information

Variables	Response	Frequency	Percentage
Age	18-20	310	38.75
	21-25	305	38.125
	26-30	185	23.125
Length of stay in the town	≤5 years	220	27.5
	> 5 years	580	72.5
Religion	Hindu	690	86.2
	Muslim	95	11.8
	Catholic	1	0.1
	Others	13	1.5
Marital status	Married	700	87.5
	Divorced	65	8.1
	Widowed	35	4.3
Educational level	Can't read and write	90	11.2
	Read and write	70	8.7
	Primary	136	17
	Secondary	190	23.7
	Preparatory	64	8

Occupation	Diploma or degree	250	31.2
	Housewife	240	30.0
	Commercial sex worker	50	6.25
	Governmental employee	230	28.75
	Merchant	199	24.875
Monthly income	Others	81	10.125
	≤ 20000	274	34.2
	20000–50000	179	21.9
	50000–200000	170	21.2
	≥ 200000	177	22.1

Table 1 has provided the information related to the demographic details of the participants. According to analysis, highest number of participants (38.75%) were aged between 18-20 years and belongs to Hindu religion (86.2%). Moreover, majority numbers of participants (55.6%) were married with diploma or degree (31.2%), followed by secondary

education (23.7%). Further, 28.75% of the participants were governmental employee, 30.0% housewife, and 24.875% merchant. Moreover, the average monthly income of participant was ≤ 20000 (34.2%) followed by 20000-50000 (21.9%) and 50000-200000 (21.2%).

Table 2: Knowledge (N=800 for first question and 500 for rest)

Variables	Response	Frequency	Percentage
Heard about cervical cancer	Yes	520	65
	No	280	35
Know the risk factors for cervical cancer	Yes	200	40
	No	300	60
Knowledge on risk factors of cervical cancer	Sexually transmitted disease	100	20
	Smoking	121	24.2
	Having multiple Sexual Partners	110	22
	Poor dietary habit	41	20.2
	Early marriage	98	19.6
	Family history of cervical cancer	20	4
	Others	18	3.6
HPV is a causative agent of cervical cancer	Yes	90	18
	No	410	82
Know common symptoms of cervical cancer	Yes	101	20.2
	No	399	79.8
Knowledge on the symptoms of cervical cancer	Intra or Post coital bleeding	158	31.6
	Bleeding after menopause	138	27.6
	Persistent blood-stained vaginal discharge	90	18
	Lower abdominal pain	70	14
	Others	44	8.8
Cervical cancer is preventable	Yes	325	65
	No	175	35
Cervical cancer is curable	Yes	212	42.4
	No	288	57.6
Heard about pap smear test	Yes	110	22
	No	390	78
If yes, where did you hear about Pap smear for the first time?	Relatives	60	12
	Friends	89	17.8
	Health workers	124	24.8
	Mass media	207	41.4
	Others	20	4
How many times should a healthy woman undergo pap smear test?	Only once	27	24.3
	Two times only	32	31.8
	At least three times and above	48	43.9

Table 2 has provided information related to knowledge of the participants about cervical cancer. According to analysis, 65% of the participants have heard about the cervical cancer and only 40% have knowledge about the risk factors involve in this disease. In addition to this, 24.2% participants had

knowledge that the major factor of risk in this disease is smoking followed by multiple sexual partner (22.0%) and poor dietary habits (20.2%). Moreover, majority of the participants (82%) didn't have an idea that HPV is an agent of cervical cancer. Further, 31.6% participants had idea that the major

symptom of cervical cancer is intra or post coital bleeding. Apart from this, 41.4% of participants

have heard about the pep smear from mass media, followed by health worker (24.8%).

Table 3: Attitude (N=500)

Variables	Response	Frequency	Percentage
Believe having multiple sexual partners is risk factor for cervical cancer	Yes	360	72
	No	140	28
Believe cervical cancer is transmittable through sexual inter course	Yes	110	22
	No	390	78
Believe HIV positivity increases the chance of getting cervical cancer	Yes	320	64
	No	180	36
Believe use of oral contraceptive pill is a risk factor for cervical cancer	Yes	70	14
	No	430	86
Think that smoking is a risk factor for cervical cancer	Yes	335	67
	No	165	33
Think early marriage is a risk factor for cervical cancer	Yes	360	72
	No	140	28
Think cervical cancer is a major health problem for female of reproductive age group	Yes	437	94.6
	No	63	12.6
Think it is possible to detect cervical cancer with early screening before symptoms appear	Yes	250	50
	No	250	50
Think early detection of cervical cancer is good for treatment out come	Yes	456	91.2
	No	44	8.8
Believe cervical cancer is preventable	Yes	390	78
	No	110	22
Think it is possible to cure cervical cancer	Yes	236	47.3
	No	264	52.7

Table 3 has analyzed the data about the attitude of participants considered for the evaluation regarding cervical cancer. As per the analysis, the attitude of participants suggested that multiple sex partner is major factor of cervical cancer. However, 78% considered that it is not transmitted through sexual intercourse. Further, 64.0% agreed that HIV positive patients have higher chances of cervical cancer and 86% participants believed that use of oral contraceptive pill does not increase the risk of cervical cancer. Additionally, 72% participants considered the early marriage is a risk factor for cervical cancer and 94.6% agreed that it's a major health problem in females from reproductive age groups.

Discussion

According to this study, 500 (65%) individuals, or more than half had heard about cervical cancer. This result is in line with research conducted in Qatar, Niger, and North Korea, where more than 85%, 72% and 62% of respondents said they were aware of cervical cancer, respectively. In terms of information, developing and under developing nations have positive trends. However, this data is insufficient to generate the understanding that the three research and this one reflects.

In addition, 65.0% stated they have heard of cervical cancer, and 42.2% participants responded that

cervical cancer is curable and avoidable, Moreover, 65.0% said that there are preventative and therapeutic measures for cervical cancer. According to a Korean study, the majority of respondents (64%) were unaware that cervical cancer can be avoided. This consistency may once more result from individuals' differing levels of knowledge across the two investigations [13]. It may also result from the absence of details regarding cervical cancer prevention and treatment.

Only 47 (43.9%) of those who had heard of the pap smear test agreed that a woman in apparent good health should get one at least three times in her lifetime. This indicates that most people who had heard of the Pap smear test were unaware of its frequency and/or how many times they should get one in their lifetime. This is in addition to the general lack of knowledge on the test. This is consistent with research from Niger and Iran, which indicate that only 50.6% and 44.3% of respondents, respectively, were aware of cervical cancer screening tests [14].

Additionally, this study attempted to evaluate the women's attitudes, and of those (500) who were aware of cervical cancer, 360 participants believe that having early marriage and numerous sexual partners are risk factors for cervical cancer. This could be attributed to the general perception in the society that any unsafe diseases are a risk factor for sexual activity. Because the community holds that

those who engage in several sexual relationships will always face consequences from God for their transgressions. Similarly, 437 (94.6%) participants thought that cervical cancer was a serious health issue in women of reproductive age group [15].

Conclusion

Participants' general understanding of cervical cancer and how to prevent it was insufficient. More than 80% of the participants were not aware that HPV is a factor that causes cervical cancer. This is really concerning because preventing HPV infection is the most effective approach to avoid cervical cancer. Apart from this, the finding of study has involved the main information source on cervical cancer was the mass media. An isolated problem cannot be solved. Moreover, governmental, and non-governmental entities as well as other concerned organisations must cooperate to raise women's broad awareness of cervical cancer and ways to avoid it.

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